

HOW TO ANALYZE GRAMMAR ACTIVITIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866884>

Learners should be taught grammar skills to be good language users to utilize words and message appropriately and make them meaningful. Learners will be able to construct better sentences in their speaking and writing outputs if they have a better understanding of grammar. To achieve to effective way of teaching grammar, teachers should have knowledge how to apply grammar activities for their learners productively. Coming from theories we learnt and personal experience, I am going to analysis some grammar activities based on three different approaches:

1. Teaching grammar as product
2. Teaching grammar as process
3. Teaching grammar as skill

Teaching grammar as a product

As a Grammar product, I analyzed the activities in Antonia Clare’s book “Speak out” for pre-intermediate level students (Appendix 1). This activity is based on implicitly noticing structure and usage of past simple. In this activity "4A", noticing is well covered. After learning the paragraph, learners encounter a past simple structure and become familiar with the structure. According to the noticing hypothesis, learners' grammatical competency will not progress until they notice how language is utilized. The underlying notion here is that students take into close consideration to the form and meaning of certain linguistic forms in input, which will help them absorb the rule (Batstone, 1996). This activity provides an opportunity to specifically notice past simple.

In this activity there is no opportunity for self-discovery. They just pay attention to the form of past simple but no interaction from students. The question is what will happen when the teacher leads the students through their exploration. When it comes to consciousness-raising, the direction is more apparent in this activity. But there are cases where students are looking around from and meaning, not exactly the point that needs to be noticed. In this activity, too, if no special emphasis is placed on the past simple, the general can be analyzed and other features can be considered. It would better if past simple words are highlighted to help them notice more quickly. In addition to creating “self-discovery” to involve the students into the context.

The next activity aims to teach relative clause (Activity 2). First students read the given sentences and complete the rules based on the relative clauses given in the example. Students explore the rules using from given examples. The first stage of this activity is really useful to notice relative clauses. Although the activity is useful for teaching tenses, if the student's skill level is a little higher, self-discovery is advised inside the activity. Rather than putting order the sentences to the supplied rules, the students must determine the rule of usage for past tense using from examples in the given sentences.

Teaching grammar as a Process

When using product-based activity, learners notice that they are able to learn more effectively by practicing the rules they have already learned. According to Batstone (1994), process teaching involves students more involved, covering communicative knowledge. If we analyze process activity, in the first activity, learners are involved to differentiate past simple and past continuous through activities (Appendix 2). Before doing this exercise, students watch a movie and discuss which films go the sentences with after doing the exercise based on that movie. In the next activity, they work in pairs and answer questions based on the communicative process. I think this task encourages learners to better understand the difference between low simple and low continuous. According to Long (1989), process teaching is beneficial because it stimulates students to push themselves to apply their language abilities in contextualized activities and communication. This is also highly relevant in these process exercises, because learners not only learn the principles of past tenses and past continuous and how to use them in sentences, but they also put both information-gap and context-gap into practice.

Teaching grammar as a Skill

Teaching grammar as a skill activity is linked to the language teaching reflective stage. According to Batstone (1994), the reflection stage allows students to demonstrate their mastery by analyzing what is said to how it should have been express. They are not provided any explanation or guidance about how to use particular grammar components in this exercise. We can say that it is the time for learners to carry his learning into action in order to fix errors during the analysis phase. In this activity, students first read the text carefully and get the main idea. Then they will be able to analyze and further strengthen the past simple structure by finding answers to questions. After the reading task, they begin to write their own travel experience. I think this productive writing activity helps to use grammar rules in context and develop creativity. As a disadvantage side, in both activities students can confront some in accuracy. They are more likely to forget particular grammar patterns when producing speech or composing text. As Batstone (1994) stated, it is advisable for the teacher to provide learners with corrective feedback to prevent such problems. For this first teacher listens the students answer then he or she can give formative feedback to make them work on their mistakes.

To improve the first activity, I would highlight all past simple forms and ask some contextualized questions in order to catch my learners' attention both form and meaning. When it comes to the use of language, activity B can be used in order to check their comprehension how they are able to use the grammar structures in their own context.

Research

In the field of teaching, it is not possible to conduct a lesson successfully with exactly one method or approach. Every teacher has their own approaches how to teach her or his learners. There are many approach and methods we can use in the lesson, but the main emphasis is on how to use them productively. According to Thornbury (2001) There are particular ways of teaching grammar: deductive (rule-driven) and inductive (rule-discovery). While some researchers prefer deductive teaching approach, others inductive one more effective to acquire language better and faster. Active manipulation requires not only noticing the structure but also being able to apply it. Batstone (1994) mentioned that there are three

approaches of grammar activities: product, process, and skill. He claims, entails emphasizing on both the meaning and the structure of the language in teaching grammar as a product. The key benefit of this method is that it helps students recognize and notice grammar functions. Batstone (1994) rates noticing as an entrance to subsequent learning process. Active manipulation requires not only noticing the structure but also being able to apply it. When it comes to teaching grammar as a process, it creates opportunity for learners to practice more on language usage which helps them proceduralize acquired knowledge. Furthermore, grammar structures should be emphasized through reading, writing or communicative skills while dealing with grammar activity as a skill (Batstone, 1996).

Conclusion

After analyzing these activities, I have seen that in order to be effective in the teaching process, it is important that the activities be contextualized and relevant. That's why I chose the activities in "Speakout" because I personally use this book for my students. Sometimes I try to modify if students have difficulty doing activities. Because I don't build appropriateness in critical thinking or communicative skill in students sometimes. Based on the current post era methods, it can be said that the inductive method is more effective than the deductive method. Another important factor is the lack of "self-discovery" in activities. As Chan, P. (2010) mentioned. grammar activities should focus more on self-discovery in order to engage the learner better in the lesson and to ensure that grammar structures are stored in long term memory. Batstone (1994) noted that it is important to set time constraints for students based on their level. The level of students in the classroom is not always the same, so lower level students need more time to complete the activity.

Appendix 1. Activities for teaching grammar as product.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY

(Antonia Clare. JJ Wilson (2012). Speak out. Pre-Intermediate students' book. 2nd edition. Pearson, p 16).

Activity 1.

4 A Find five mistakes in this paragraph.

F

?

I met Layla at a market. She was selling bread. We started chatting and got well on. At the time I didn't keep a girlfriend, so I asked her on a date. We went to a local bakery! We soon fell to love and I proposed at her after a month. I hid the ring in a piece of cake. Fortunately, she accepted, and she didn't eat the ring! It was a good way to get engaged. A week later we became married.

Activity 2

GRAMMAR
RELATIVE CLAUSES

3 Read sentences 1–5 and complete the rules below.

- 1 He included a poem **which** contained clues.
- 2 There are blogs **that** describe Fenn's treasure hunt.
- 3 Tourism has increased, thanks to people **who** want to find the chest.
- 4 He has received more than 13,000 emails from people **that** want more clues.
- 5 He probably hid it in New Mexico, **where** he lives.

RULES

Relative clauses tell you:

- which thing, person or place we are talking about.
- what a thing, person or place is or does.

Use ¹ which or ² _____ for things.

Use ³ _____ or ⁴ _____ for people.

Use ⁵ _____ for places.

Appendix 2. Activities for teaching grammar as process.
(Antonia Clare. JJ Wilson (2012). Speak out. Pre-Intermediate students' book. 2nd edition. Pearson, p 56).
Activity 2A and B.

2 A Put the verbs in brackets into the past simple or past continuous.

- 1 While they (walk), they (see) a fence.
While they were walking, they saw a fence.
- 2 While they (cross) the sea, a terrible storm nearly (destroy) the raft.
- 3 They (run) away one night while it (rain).
- 4 While he (wander) in the wilderness, he (meet) some people who helped him.
- 5 When the men (sail) on the ocean, they (see) many sea creatures.
- 6 While he (live) in an abandoned bus, he (realise) he might die.

B Work in pairs. Discuss. Which films from Lesson 5.1 do the sentences go with?

3 Work in pairs and take turns. Ask and answer the question. Where were you and what were you doing at these times yesterday?

6:00	10:00	13:00
16:00	19:00	22:00

Appendix 2. Activities for teaching grammar as a skill.

(Antonia Clare, JJ Wilson (2012). *Speak out. Pre-Intermediate students' book. 2nd edition. Pearson, p 95).*

Activity 8A and B.

8 A Read the travel blog. Which country did Lia visit? Did she enjoy the experience? Why/Why not?

Posted by Lia on December 14th, 2015 Previous post >> Next post >>

Day 4

Today was our final day trekking along the Great Wall of China and it was probably one of the hardest days we've had. Today we walked for more than 12 km over 8 hours in very hot and humid temperatures. We climbed thousands of steps and some parts of the Wall had no sides, just a very long drop on either side. It was terrifying. However, the views were spectacular and when we finally reached the watch tower, where we stopped for lunch and took some photos, we all felt incredibly proud of what we had achieved. Sitting on top of the Wall, looking down on the fields and listening to the silence is a feeling I don't think I'll ever forget.

B Choose a place you have visited. Write about your experience. Use these questions to help you.

- 1 Where did you go?
- 2 When?
- 3 Who with?
- 4 Why was it an amazing experience?
- 5 Would you like to go again?

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